

Palatal Morphology and Its Relative Effect on Malocclusion A Review

Anusha Jaiswal¹
Pradeep Raghav²
Ruchi Saini³
C Munish Reddy⁴
Anwasha Garg⁵

PG Student¹
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut, Uttar Pradesh

Professor & HOD²
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut, Uttar Pradesh

Associate Professor³
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut, Uttar Pradesh

Professor⁴
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut, Uttar Pradesh

PG Student⁵
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

Craniofacial structures, including the human palate, exhibit unique morphological variations. Palatal morphology influences malocclusion and is affected by factors such as breathing, tongue posture, and dental habits. This review explores literature on palatal morphology, focusing on arch form, length, depth, and rugae patterns, and their impact on dentoalveolar and skeletal patterns. A four-month search identified relevant studies from PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar, with fifteen articles selected for analysis. Findings indicate significant variations in palatal morphology across malocclusion classes and skeletal growth patterns. Class I malocclusions have larger maxillary bases and intermolar widths compared to Class II and III. Class II division 1 malocclusions show greater palatal height and narrower maxillary arches, while Class II division 2 exhibits wider arches and lower palatal heights. Unique and stable palatal rugae serve as reliable identification markers in forensic medicine. Advances in imaging techniques have enhanced understanding, aiding in diagnosis and tailored treatments.

Keywords - Palatal Morphology, Malocclusion, Skeletal Growth Pattern.

Introduction

Each person is born with unique craniofacial structures, formulations, and facial characteristics that distinguish them from others.¹ The human palate, with its complex morphology and functional importance, is crucial for speech articulation and maintaining occlusal harmony. Palatal morphology, characterized by its shape, size, and structural variations, has long been implicated in the etiology of malocclusion a complex dental anomaly affecting millions worldwide. Many factors, including breathing pattern, tongue posture and size, dental inclination, occlusion, and parafunctional behaviours, have influence on its irregular form². Malocclusions in three dimensions (3D) often occur at the same time and usually interrelate with each other. Growth follows the sequential completion of the cranium followed by facial width (transverse), then facial depth (sagittal), and finally facial height (vertical).

Transverse growth highlights dentofacial asymmetries, jaw expansion or constriction, and dental crossbites. Sagittal growth provides insights into facial profiles, arch length discrepancies, and overjet issues. Vertical growth patterns reveal facial proportions, deep bites, and open bites.

Transverse growth is nearly complete by late adolescence, whereas sagittal and vertical growth continue well into adulthood. Therefore, a lack of maxillary transverse width will affect the vertical and sagittal development of maxillofacial bone in the early stages, which is hard to perceive. Malocclusion usually occurs in mixed dentition or permanent dentition when the transverse development approaches completion. For this situation, patients usually did not

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report the insufficient transverse width but the sagittal problem as their main complaint, so clinicians were often more likely to pay attention to the sagittal dimension³. However, more recently, the contributions of maxillary expansion have become well known among dental professionals. When deciding between non extraction with maxillary expansion and extraction treatments in borderline patients, clinicians should carefully diagnose and select a plan based on the patient's maxillary width. This review article aims to provide an comprehensive overview of the current literature pertaining to palate morphology such as the arch form, length, depth, the rugae patterns, and its effects on dentoalveolar and skeletal patterns.

Methods

Research publications were searched for 4-months on PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar and the articles with the terms palatal morphology, palatal vault, arch form and malocclusions were collected. Furthermore, all the articles were analyzed to determine the relationship between palatal morphology and malocclusion.

Results

Finally, Fifteen relevant articles were selected to formulate this review.

Discussion

Palatal Morphology

The hard palate, a bone wall that separates the mouth and nasal cavities, acts both the oral cavity's roof and the nasal cavity's bottom. The palatal processes of the maxillary bones make up the front section of the hard palate, whereas the horizontal plates of the palatal bones create the posterior (distal) section. The shape of the palatal vault shows great variability.⁴

Palate expansion mainly occurs during the first 5 years of life at the intermaxillary and interpalatine sutures. Later, width increases are due to bone growth on the outer surfaces of the maxillary bones and the eruption of permanent teeth, resulting in up to a 2.2 mm increase in intermolar width. These changes are associated with the vertical growth of the alveolar process, which diverges to form the palatal walls. A narrow or triangular palate often indicates an abnormal tongue position, as the tongue rests on the floor of the mouth instead of the palatal rugae, exerting pressure on the teeth. A low tongue position may lead to lower dental arch expansion and upper arch collapse.⁵

In primary dentition, Hughes et al (2001) found that genetic factors significantly influence variation in maxillary arch width; Eguchi et al (2004) found that there is

significant additive genetic variance in maxillary arch width, depth, and palatal height in teenage twins. Palate growth is influenced by both genetic and environmental factors, determined by a complex interaction of factors including developmental timing, soft tissue influences, and growth peak period.⁶

According to Harvold et al., the shape of the maxillary arch is largely influenced by tongue posture and movements, particularly during key stages of dental development such as the complete eruption of the maxillary first molars. In children undergoing growth, local factors like muscle recruitment and respiratory patterns, as well as genetic factors affecting cell responsiveness, influence palatal vault development. Similarly, Lione et al. found that mouth breathing during growth led to distinct palatal morphology, characterized by a narrower and higher vault compared to nose breathing individuals.⁷

Palatal rugae, unique crests similar to fingerprints, are located on either side of the palatine raphe past the incisive papilla. They remain stable despite tooth changes, making them ideal for analysis. Typically numbering three to five per side, they do not extend past the anterior half of the hard palate or cross the midline. An increased size of palatal rugae has been linked to the presence of an open bite.⁸ Thomas (1983) observed that palatal rugae remain unchanged except in length, likely due to underlying growth. Comparative studies across diverse Indian populations, including Karnataka, Kerala, and Manipur, revealed significant differences in rugae patterns. M Selvamani et al. found that females from Kerala had a greater number of primary rugae compared to males.⁹

Relationship between Palatal Morphology and Malocclusion

Facial forms are one of the first parameters assessed by orthodontists during their initial extra-oral examination. The various types of facial forms as proposed by Martin (1957)⁴⁸ through facial indices are leptoprosopic, euryprosopic, and mesoprosopic. Individuals with these facial forms present with unique facial features and intraoral findings. Leptoprosopic individuals have deeper palatal arches, a tendency towards constricted basal arch forms and are more towards the hyperdivergent growth pattern. Euryprosopic individuals have shallower palatal arches with wider basal arch forms and have a more horizontal or hypodivergent growth pattern. (Christie, 1977)¹⁰.

Parcha et al. (2017) explored the relationship between facial forms and palate depth in children and adolescents. They found that high angle cases tended to have higher and narrower palates, while low angle cases were associated with shallower and wider palates. Children generally had longer and shallower palates compared to adolescents, likely due to bone growth and palate remodeling.

Palatal depth assessment typically involves qualitative categorization as high, moderate, or shallow. In 1939, Korkhaus introduced a quantitative method the Korkhaus Palatal Index to measure palate depth and arch width reliably. Palates were classified as high (> 22 mm), moderate (19–22 mm), or shallow (< 19 mm) using this index. The palatometer was employed to measure depth, with the central fossa of 1st molars as a reference for arch width. The normal palatal index, calculated by dividing arch width by palate depth, is around 42%, aiding in identifying transverse arch width issues. Korkhaus Palatal Index was found to be significantly larger in Class II division 1 malocclusion 45.06 ± 4.94 (%) as compared to Class I malocclusion 42.58 ± 3.21 (%). One potential drawback of this method was that the inclination of the molars was not taken into consideration. Hence, it would not give a correct assessment of the arch width and values indicating either expansion or constriction¹⁰

Prasanna et al. (2020) conducted a CBCT retrospective study on hyperdivergent patients, aiming to correlate molar inclination with palatal depth and assess transverse discrepancies. They found a significant correlation between molar inclination and palatal depth in vertical growers ($P < 0.05$). Increased palatal depth corresponded to greater buccolingual inclination of first molars, suggesting increased buccal flaring and buccal root torque. This study aligns with Mitra and Ravi (2011)¹⁰, who noted increased palatal inclination of molars in short faced individuals. Conversely, Janson et al. (2004)¹⁰ suggested notable buccal inclination in maxillary second molars among long-faced individuals.

Palate depth, arch width, and molar inclinations guide treatment decisions. Assessing arch width, especially if it's mildly reduced (based on palatal index), alongside molar inclinations, informs whether tipping alone can correct transverse discrepancies or if more substantial expansion via devices like Hyrax or MARPE is needed. Southard et al. (2019)¹¹ differentiated dental and skeletal crossbites. Decompensating molar inclinations resolves dental crossbites positively but worsens skeletal ones. CBCT aids in assessing molar inclinations,

identifying arch width, and confirming periodontal biotype, crucial for adults to avoid complications like fenestration and dehiscence due to excessive buccal crown torque¹⁰.

Laganà et al.¹² utilized geometric morphometric analysis (GMM) to compare palatal shape variations between open bite and control subjects. Results revealed a marked constriction of the maxillary arch in open bite subjects compared to controls with normal occlusion. Interestingly, palatal shape variations in the open bite group were unaffected by non-nutritive sucking habits.

Huang X. et al studied palatal morphology in skeletal Class I and Class II subjects with retrusive mandibles. They found males had a generally higher and wider posterior palate than females, regardless of sagittal and vertical patterns. In skeletal Class II subjects, males with hyperdivergent and normodivergent patterns had a higher, narrower posterior palate, while females had a higher palate without significant narrowing compared to hypodivergent subjects. Overall, skeletal Class II subjects had a flatter, narrower posterior palate than Class I subjects. The study concluded that sagittal and vertical patterns significantly impact palatal morphology, with increased vertical dimensions linked to a higher, narrower palate¹³

Buschang P.H. et al (1994)¹⁴ conducted a study on dental arch morphology, palatal height, and incisor irregularity in adult females. The study found that younger age groups had significantly larger maxillary and mandibular arches, while the oldest group had shorter and wider arches. Palatal height was greatest in the youngest and least in the oldest group. Class II subjects had smaller arches, greater maxillary incisor irregularity, and less mandibular incisor irregularity compared to Class I subjects. Additionally, Class II division 1 subjects had greater palatal heights and longer, narrower maxillary arches than Class II division 2 subjects.

There are also significant differences in arch size and shape between subjects with Class I and Class II malocclusion. The maxillary arch is significantly larger in Class I than in Class II malocclusion, females with Class II division 2 malocclusion have the smallest maxillary arches. The longer, narrower maxillary arches of Class II division 1 females suggest that posterior posturing of the mandible may be necessary to maintain occlusal contacts. Mandibular arch size is greatest for Class II division 1 patients, followed by Class I and Class II division 2, respectively. This result can be explained by the fact that the etiology of Class II malocclusion is related to mandibular retrognathism, maxillary

prognathism, or a combination.¹⁴

Skeletal Class III malocclusion is characterized by maxillomandibular disharmony and a distinctive palatal shape compared to other skeletal patterns. Chen et al. studied the dental arches and skeletal bases in untreated Class III subjects, finding that the maxillary skeletal base and intermolar widths were significantly smaller in the Class III group compared to the Class I group, whereas mandibular intermolar widths did not differ significantly between the groups.¹⁵ Lateral cephalograms are the standard for studying craniofacial morphology in Class III subjects. However, conventional cephalometry and dental cast analysis, relying on angular and linear measurements, are insufficient for analyzing complex anatomical shape changes.

Ahn et al.¹⁵ analyzed CBCT and maxillary study models to investigate the relationship between palatal morphology and facial skeletal patterns in adult patients with Class III malocclusion. They found that increased transverse facial skeletal width was associated with narrow, deep, and long palates. Similarly, Paoloni et al.¹⁵ observed in growing Class III malocclusion subjects that increases in angle divergence correlated with narrow and high palates, indicating a significant covariation between palatal and craniofacial morphology.

Clinical Implications

Palatal morphology significantly influences an individual's skeletal and facial patterns and it can be influenced by orthodontic treatment. Hence, analysis of osseous or dental arch dimensions is fundamental in orthodontic treatment planning.

Currently, the need for palatal expansion treatment in mixed dentition is increasing. Early treatment with palatal expansion eliminates crossbites in an effort to guide normal occlusal development. Additionally, in patients with crowding, expansion increases space to avoid the need for extraction and jaw surgery in adult orthodontic treatments.⁶ There are various types of expansion treatments available, but most result in the buccal inclination of the molars that leads to relapse. Lemos et al. (2018) compared two types of expanders, Haas-type and Hyrax-type, finding that the latter poses a higher risk of root and alveolar bone resorption due to molar force exertion. Clinical success has been reported using bone-borne palatal expanders with mini-implants, suggesting their effectiveness in correcting transverse maxillary defects in adults. It's crucial for treatments to improve both occlusal function and palatal morphology. Despite this, many researchers have noted that expansion treatment during mixed dentition can lead to buccal

inclination in the maxillary first molar, resulting in multiple relapses. Achieving long-term stable palatal expansion without molar inclination is desirable.

The stability of palatal rugae even after orthodontic treatment has made them reliable identification markers. Various classification systems have been used to study the gross anatomy of human palatal rugae, showing good reproducibility and short-term stability. Consequently, rugae patterns are utilized in forensic medicine for identifying individuals from dental casts post-mortem.¹¹

Conclusion

- Class I malocclusion was found to have significantly larger maxillary skeletal base and intermolar widths compared to Class II and Class III malocclusions.
- Class II division 1 malocclusion showed greater palatal height and a narrower maxillary arch compared to Class II division 2. This insufficient transverse development and increased palatal height resulted in a significantly larger Korkhaus Palatal Index in Class II division 1 than in Class I malocclusion.
- Along with this, skeletal growth patterns also have an influence on palatal morphology. Where it was observed that individuals having leptoprosopic facial form and hyperdivergent growth pattern have deeper palatal arches and constricted basal arch form whereas individuals having euryprosopic facial pattern and hypodivergent growth pattern have shallow palatal arches and wider basal arch form.
- Skeletal open bite is linked to deeper palatal arches and constricted basal arch forms, while skeletal deep bite is associated with shallow palatal arches and wider basal arch forms.
- The consistent stability of palatal rugae even after orthodontic treatment makes them reliable identification markers, which is why they are used in forensic medicine for identifying individuals from dental casts post-mortem.

Advanced imaging techniques have revolutionized the understanding of palatal morphology, enabling more accurate diagnoses and personalized treatments. Longitudinal studies on craniofacial growth and palatal morphology will enhance these insights, refine treatment strategies, and promote oral health and overall well-being.

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